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after all, witch tea is drunk

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Photo: Niele Newton (Art | Adriane)

Keywords: Concentration variations; Traditional medicine; Drying process; Cytotoxicity.

Introduction

Ayahuasca tea is a decoction prepared with leaves of *P. viridis* shrub popularly known as rainha, chacrona or chacruna and stems of *B. caapi* commonly known as mariri, ayahuasca, caapi, jagube (Callaway et al., 1999b; Miranda et al., 2020). The decoction of the plants together is the traditional way of preparing Ayahuasca. This tea has been used in traditional indigenous medicine of the Amazonian peoples for healing and also in spiritual rituals since pre-Columbian times (Estrella-Parra et al., 2019; Miller et al., 2019). In several countries, such as Colombia, Peru and Brazil it is the fundamental element of indigenous cultures (Gaujac et al., 2012; Labate & Feeney, 2012). The preparation is highlighted for the psychoactive potential triggered by the synergism of the compounds *NN*-dimethyltryptamine alkaloids (DMT) present in *Psychotria viridis* leaves together with the β -carbolinic group compounds: harmine (HRM), harmaline (HRL), and tetrahydroharmine (THH), found in the stems of *Banisteriopsis caapi* (Fig. 1). The synergistic activity of these compounds confers psychotropic and entheogenic effects (Tupper, 2008) considered by tea consumers as a result of consciousness expansion.

Figure 1. Chemical structures donate *NN*-dimethyltryptamine (DMT), β -carbolinic harmine (HRM), harmaline (HRL) and tetrahydroharmine (THH) alkaloids.

The incorporation of this beverage for healing purposes and religious support in urban contemporary society emerged from indigenous and *caboclas* populations of tropical forests. Studies of the bioactive compounds of Ayahuasca tea (Callaway et al., 1999; Kaasik et al., 2021) and of the plants that are used for the preparation (Cavalcante et al., 2018; Miranda et al., 2020) were prompted by increased religious and therapeutic use of Ayahuasca in the United States and several other countries in Europe, but also by the worldwide trend for psychedelic therapy research. The entheogenic effect of Ayahuasca was attributed to a direct relationship with DMT content, that when taken orally is inactivated by monoamine visceral oxidase (MAO).

This effect is reversed by the action of β -carbolines, which are highly active reversible MAO inhibitors, protecting DMT from deamination by MAO, enabling the beverage's oral use (McKenna, 2004a).

Concentration variations of DMT, HRM, HRL and HHT alkaloids were found in Ayahuasca samples consumed in European countries, and in some cases, synthetic product were also detected (Kaasik et al., 2021). Ayahuasca tea consumed in these countries, is known to be generally produced in Amazonian countries and shipped abroad. Silveira et al. (2020) quantified the alkaloids in Ayahuasca samples stored throughout seven days at high temperature, mimicking the mail transportation conditions, not finding any significant decrease of DMT, whereas meaningful variations of β -carbolines alkaloids were detected, with detection of HHT decrease of up to 67.9%. Other studies have also detected concentrations variations of these alkaloids in Ayahuasca samples of the same source (Pires et al., 2009). In samples prepared by traditional ritualistic procedures, which consists in the decoction of *P. viridis* leaves together with the stems of *B. caapi*, alkaloid variation reached a tenfold magnitude (Souza et al., 2019).

The literature data together with the breakthrough use of this tea acknowledged the need to establish quality control parameters for the use of Ayahuasca beverages. The first point refers to the alkaloids variations in the tea found worldwide, with another issue referring to strategies to ensure that no adulteration has been introduced to Ayahuasca beverages consumed in other countries outside the Amazon regions. Ensuring the effect of Ayahuasca traditionally used by amazon peoples. Other authors have described the great variability of *B. caapi*, with at least 30 different varieties described and cataloged, which have a direct relationship with different levels of alkaloids found in Ayahuasca preparations, aside from various plant proportion used by the different groups (Santos et al., 2020; McKenna, 2004).

Regarding origin, plant-environment relationship interferes with the secondary metabolism process, acting as a driving force for the biosynthesis of phytochemicals in plants (Ncube et al., 2012; Osbourn et al., 2003).

This approach was reported by Miranda et al., (2020) for *P. viridis*, the species that contributes with DMT, but in this study the authors did not report the alkaloid content in the tea. Another factor that influences secondary plant metabolism is the genetic diversity within the species, well described for the species used in the Ayahuasca beverage and for other medicinal species (Figueira et al., 2010; Santos et al., 2020). To ensure a safe use of Ayahuasca in countries outside the geographical area of naturally occurring plants (Europe and North America), a strategy would be to provide inputs for the preparation of Ayahuasca *in loco* at these destinations. To achieve a quality product that provides the expected effect an alternative is to provide the dehydrated and stabilized plant inputs. The drying process generates a stable product that could be easily shipped, with a reduced volume compared to the fresh plant, furthermore, the plant would be available during the whole year long (Orphanides et al., 2016). Despite being considered one of the most usual and fundamental processes for preserving medicinal plants, drying can exacerbate loss of bioactive compounds depending on the temperature applied (Chua et al., 2019).

The interference of both the environment and drying condition in the concentrations of bioactive compounds from medicinal plants is well documented (Liebelt et al., 2019; Ng et al., 2020). Despite the increased consumption of Ayahuasca in various extra-Amazonian countries, as well as their described pharmacological and therapeutic potential, yet data establishing the contribution of the local effect on the variation of alkaloid content in *B. caapi* and *P. viridis* are still to be determined. Nevertheless, there are few studies that access these plants' drying temperature parameters.

In order to standardize parameters of the inputs used in the preparation of Ayahuasca tea, herein the evaluation of the concentration of DMT, HRM, HRL and THH (Fig. 1) from plants collected in two different ecosystems in the Amazon region jointly with the influence of drying temperatures on the content of these alkaloids in the final product are reported. Furthermore, Ayahuasca tea cytotoxicity on keratinocyte cells prepared with both fresh and dried plants was tested.

2. Material and method

2.1 Collection areas and plant material

Wild *B. caapi* and cultivated *P. viridis* samples from two distinct ecosystems were collected, located 360 km apart from each other. One of the locations was *Campinarana* (CAMP), stationed south of Roraima State (00°57'03" N and 59°54'39" O) and the other was *Terra Firme* (TF), located in the North of the State of Amazonas (02°02'04" S; 60°01' O). Both sites share the same broad climate type, considered as humid equatorial Af, according to Koppen (Zarur, 1943), without clear stabilization seasons and marked by annual rain seasonally (Alvares et al., 2013). Each ecosystem in this study was characterized according to data previously described in the literature (Ab'Saber, 2002; Barbosa & Miranda, 2004; Miranda et al., 2020) and by field observations.

For all analyzes, the plant material was collected from individuals randomly chosen within each area, five individuals of wild *B. caapi* and 20 *P. viridis* trees cultivated in an agroforest, between 6 and 10 am in August/2016, January/2017, November/2017 and February/2019 were collected.

Species names were verified in <http://www.theplantlist.org> and the material identified under Voucher INPA No. 282931, 282932, 282933, 282934, 282935, deposited in the Herbarium of National Institute of Research of the Amazonia (INPA).

2.2 Pre-processing of plants and preparation of Ayahuasca

After each collection, the leaves and stems samples were washed in running water. Thereafter, *B. caapi* stems were pre-processed by smashing the shoots with wooden sticks for the separation of fibers. During pre-processing of the plant material collected in January/2016, August/2016 and November/2017, the leaves and stems were weighed separately, and then divided the samples of each species into two batches of equal weights. The first batch was used to prepare Ayahuasca with fresh plants, whereas the second batch was subjected to drying at temperatures of 60 °C, 50°C and 40°C before tea preparation. Finally, the resulting tea was analyzed to determine the DMT, HRM, HRL, and HHT alkaloid content.

The other samples were gathered in November/2017 and February/ 2019 being pre-processed as previously described, however *B. caapi* an *P. viridis* leaves were subjected to three different drying conditions: a) stems at 45 °C and leaves 40 °C; (b) stems and leaves in the sun and; (c) stems at 45 °C and leaves at 43°C. After drying, this material was used to prepare Ayahuasca beverage and determine alkaloid content.

For drying purposes, a forced circulation oven with air renewal and controlled temperature (TE 394/3 Tecnal) was used. A mesh trays was used for drying plant material in the sun. Drying was monitored by weighing samples using a precision weighing-scale at 12 h intervals and then reduced to 6 h when the material reached 50% of the initial weight, maintaining this interval until constant weight. After complete drying, the plant materials were packed in plastic bags, protected from light and stored in boxes until the time of use.

The maximum moisture content of the plants was measured according to Silveira et al. (2013). The *B. caapi* stems and *P. viridis* leaves samples were submerged in water for saturation until reaching constant weight, consider in this the maximum fresh weight (FW).

To determine dry weight (DW), the samples were dried in forced circulation oven with air renewal (TE 394/3 Tecnal) at 90°C for stems and 70°C for leaves.

Weighing was carried out at a 24h interval, being considered dry weight when the difference between two consecutive weightings was less than 1%. Maximum moisture content (MC) was calculated as $MC (\%) = (FW - DW)/FW \times 100$.

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Ayahuasca, either with fresh or dehydrated plants, was prepared following the ritual adopted by the *Centro Espírita Beneficente União do Vegetal* (CBUDV) with define proportions of *P. viridis* leaves and *B. caapi* stems and water volume, whereas fire pressure and cooking time remained constant in all preparations for analysis. The average yield was 5-7 L of tea for each batch. Ayahuasca was then stored in a plastic container while still warm (about 60°C), without air inside the bottle to minimize the process of fermentation. Thereafter the samples were left to cool at room temperature and subsequently stored at 5°C.

2.3 High Performance Liquid Chromatography Analysis with UV-vis Detector with Diodes Arrangement (HPLC-DAD)

2.3.1 Sample preparation

The liquid samples of Ayahuasca were concentrated under vacuum (FISATON®) until attaining approximately 10% of the initial volume. They were then stored in appropriate containers and frozen at - 80 °C and further freeze-dried at 4 atm pressure for 72 hours.

The samples were stored, protected from light, at 5 °C. Aliquots (10 ± 1 mg) of each Ayahuasca sample were weighed, transferred into a volumetric flask (10 mL) and dissolved in HPLC grade methanol under vigorous stirring (vortex) using ultrasound (10 min), adjusting the final volume to 10 mL (1 mg/mL stock solution). At the time of analysis, an aliquot (200 µL) of each stock solution was mixed with HPLC grade methanol (800 µL) in a 2 mL conical polypropylene tube under vortexing (1,400 rpm, 10 min) and centrifuged (12,000 rpm, 5 min). Thereafter an aliquot (200 µL) from each supernatant was transferred to a glass autosampler bottle containing 800 µL of methanol and homogenized by vortex for further analysis.

2.4 Preparation of Standard Solutions

The harmine (HRM) and harmaline (HRL) standards were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Steinheim, Germany), and Tetrahydroharmine (HHT) from Cayman Chemical, whereas *N, N*-dimethyltryptamine (DMT) was synthesized by the tryptamine dimethylation method (Giumanini et al., 1980; Pires et al., 2009). For each analyte a calibration curve containing five points was plotted, ranging from 100 to 1000 µg/mL, obtained through linear regression (the area under the curve versus concentration), considering $R^2 \geq 0.98$.

2.5 Analysis conditions by High Performance Liquid Chromatography Analysis with UV-vis with Diode Array Detection (HPLC-DAD)

Lanaro et al. (2015) described the method used. The experiment was carried out using a HPLC Proeminence System (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan). An Atlantis T3 column (150 x 3.0mm, 3µm) equipped with an Atlantis T3 protection column (30 x10 mm, 5 µm) (Waters Corporation, Milford, MA, USA) maintained at 35 °C. The mobile phase was a solution of phosphoric acid in ultrapure water (10 mmol/L, pH adjusted to 3.0 with triethylamine, A) and HPLC grade acetonitrile (B). Gradient elution, with a flow rate of 1 mL/min, started

with 40% A and 60% B maintained for 1 min and then a gradual change to 5% A and 95% B over the next 13 min., with this final proportion being maintained for 5 min. The column was rebalanced to 60% B over 0.5 min and maintained at those concentrations for 3 min (total gradient time = 21 min).

The temperature of the auto sampler was not controlled, and the injection volume was 10 µL. The diode array detector at 35 ° C was adjusted to acquire spectra from 195 to 600 nm. For quantification, the chromatograms were obtained at 279 nm (DMT), 291 nm (tetrahydroharmine), 320 nm (harmine) and 375 nm (harmaline).

2.6 *In vitro* cytotoxicity assessment

2.6.1 Cell lineage

For assessing the antiproliferative activity, a human non-tumor lineage (HaCaT, immortal keratinocytes) was used, which was provided by the Faculty of Dentistry of Piracicaba - FOP/Unicamp. The cell line was grown in T75 flasks (Corning) in complete medium (RPMI-1640, supplemented with 5% fetal bovine serum and 1% penicillin /streptomycin) at 37 °C under humid atmosphere supplemented with 5% CO₂. These conditions were used both for the maintenance of the cells and for the experiments. The cells were used between passages 5 and 12.

2.6.2 Assessment of cytotoxicity

Briefly, the HaCaT cells were seeded in 96-well plates (T1 plates, between 3 to 6×10^4 cells/mL, $100 \mu\text{L}$ /well), incubated for 24 h, treated with freeze-dried Ayahuasca sample (0.15, 1.5, 15 and $150 \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) and doxorubicin (0.015, 0.15, 1.5 and $15 \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, $100 \mu\text{L}/\text{mL}$ in triplicate), and then incubated for 48 h at 37°C in 5% CO_2 . A second plate, denominated T0, was prepared to infer the absorbance value of untreated cells at the moment of sample addition. Untreated (T0 and T1 plates) and treated (T1 plates) cells were fixed with 50% trichloroacetic acid and stained with sulforhodamine dye (0.4% in acetic acid 1%).

Absorbance was recorded at 540 nm using a microplate reader (Molecular Devices®, VersaMax model). Using the absorbance values, the cell growth (%), at each sample concentration, was calculated considering at 100% of cell growth the difference between the absorbances of untreated cells after 48 h incubation (T1) and at the sample addition moment (T0). The curve cell growth vs. sample concentration was plotted and GI50 (concentration required for 50% growth inhibition) was calculated by sigmoidal regression using the Origin 8.0 software (Origin Lab Corporation, Northampton, MA, USA). These analyzes were performed at the Laboratory of Phytochemistry, Pharmacology and Experimental Toxicology (LAFTEX) at the Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences at UNICAMP.

3. Results and discussion

This work allowed to verify the influence of the environment and the drying process of *Banisteriopssis caapi* stem and *Psychotria viridis* leaves in the concentration of four alkaloids present in Ayahuasca tea, prepared according to traditional ritual. Considering the great interest in the use of Ayahuasca for religious purposes and for treating various neurological and psychiatric conditions, studies of these variables provide important contributions to establish the necessary parameters to ensure reproducibility of the psychotropic and pharmacological effects (Breeksema et al., 2020; Estrella-Parra et al., 2019; Hamill et al., 2019; Miranda et al., 2020; Orsolini et al., 2020; Romeo et al., 2020; Santos & Hallak, 2020).

Herein two plant species collected from two sites in the northern region of Brazil were evaluated. The ecosystems were from North of Amazonas State, in Terra-Firme (TF) and another in the South of Roraima State in Campinarana (CAMP). The TF region exhibits an average annual rainfall of 2,585 mm and soil water retention capacity greater than the CAMP ecosystem that has an average. annual rainfall rate of 1,847 mm, which is approximately 30% less than TF (Agritempo, 2018).

CAMP has even a longer summer period (Miranda et al., 2020; Moreira, 2016), the soil is poor in minerals and there is high leaching caused by the water intensity of rainfall (Rodrigues et al., 2001; Silveira et al., 2013). These factors together make the plants from CAMP ecosystem to suffer a period of water stress, which does not occur with the TF plants. These ecosystems are located geographically on opposite sides of the Equator, therefore, summer (less rainy) and winter (more rainy) seasons are inverted in both areas.

November is the only month in which the summer period occurs simultaneously in the two ecosystems, but at opposite stages of the season, one in the beginning of the season whereas the other at the end of the season.

Plant-environment relationship interferes secondary metabolites produced by the plants (Osborn et al., 2003) and has been the target of study for many species over time (Liebelt et al., 2019; Liesenfeld et al., 2019; Liu et al., 2016; Ncube et al., 2012).

In addition to the environmental characteristics (geographical origin of the plant) and the collection period of the plants used in the preparation of the tea, the genetic diversity of the species, the post-harvest processes, such as drying, as well as the conditions of tea preparation also influence the final tea entheogenic substances content.

The amount and proportion of plants used in the preparation of Ayahuasca are parameters that influence directly in the content of alkaloids detected in the beverage (McKenna, 2004b). Among the alkaloids extracted by the decoction process, compounds HRL and HRM are easily degraded into THH because of the temperature effect (Callaway, 2005). In an attempt to minimize variability in the results and respecting the ritualistic preparation method used by UDV, all Ayahuasca tea preparations in this study sought to standardize the proportion of plants, the initial volume of water, the intensity of fire, and the final yield.

Furthermore, all Ayahuasca tea samples were stored at -5°C before the freeze-drying process. Stability studies of samples monitored by Liquid Chromatography coupled to Mass Spectrometry (LC-ESI-MS/MS) showed that DMT and HRM alkaloids were stable over a period of 12 months when stored under refrigerated conditions. However, HRL and HHT were easily degraded. The content of HHT significantly dropped within a four-month interval, with different profiles among the evaluated samples (Silveira et al., 2020).

The results produced herein evidence that parameters such as the place and time of collection as well as the effect of the drying process on the concentration of alkaloids in the Ayahuasca tea prepared for this study cause different outcomes. The psychotropic effect of Ayahuasca tea depends on the synergic activity of the secondary metabolites, among them harmine (HRM), harmaline (HRL), tetrahydroharmine (HHT), and the *N,N*-dimethyltryptamine (DMT) (Estrella-Parra et al., 2019). Therefore, the variation of the gross and relative levels of these four alkaloids in Ayahuasca tea prepared with plants collected in *Campinarana* and *Terra-firme* were evaluated.

Considering Ayahuasca samples prepared with fresh plants collected in the winter (Table 1, samples A3 and A4), the concentration of DMT, HRL and THH were 54.22, 50.09 and 42.09%, respectively; being higher in TF plants, whereas HRM concentration was similar for both ecosystems. However, when the plants were collected during the summer (Table 1, Samples A2 and A13), an increase in DMT concentration (44.34%); decrease in the concentrations of HRL and HRM (46.83 and 48.04%, respectively) with maintenance of THH concentration when comparing TF and CAMP was observed. Furthermore, when comparing two different years of harvesting in the same season (summer) (Table 1, samples A5 and

A13 from CAMP and A2 and A7 from TF), samples A13 and A5 showed an increase of 49.6% in DMT content and 5.6% for THH, with a decrease in HRL levels of 19.68% and for HRM of 20.58%.

Whereas a 24% decrease in DMT and 11.84% HHT in samples A2 and A7 with a concomitant increase to 35.47% and 14.93% for HRL and HRM content was detected, showing how climatic inter-annual variations in water availability in the soil directly influence the content of alkaloids (Tab.2).

The significant decrease in soil water availability from January to November in the CAMP ecosystem was reflected in the samples with a decrease of 24% in DMT and 14.93% in HRM, whereas for TF samples, where the soil water availability variation was positive, an increase of 49.6% was observed for DMT and 5.6% for THH.

Previous analysis of several Ayahuasca samples obtained during five years from different religious groups revealed wide variation in the alkaloid profile (Callaway et al., 2005). Moreover, Ayahuasca plants showed marked alkaloid concentration variations when collected in different seasons at the same site (Lanaro et al., 2015). These studies based their results on the different forms of preparation, the sources and the quantity/proportion of the plants used in Ayahuasca preparation. Variations found in this study are smaller than those found by Callaway and Lanaro (Table 3).

Considering that herein standardized samples were used from the plant collection site to the preparation of Ayahuasca tea from a single religious source, the alkaloids variation levels found in this study are directly related to the season of collection and to the characteristics of the environment where the plants were obtained. Standardizing the proportions of plants used in the preparation of Ayahuasca, in an attempt to increase consumption safety and control the concentration of entheogenic compounds must necessarily consider the place and time of harvest (Liebelt et al., 2019).

The concentrations of HRM, HRL, and THH alkaloids detected showed that the conversion of HRM into HRL and from this to THH during decoction, as suggested by Callaway, (2005), in our samples occurred in a lower scale as detected for HRM and HRL content in the tea samples evaluated. This reinforces the importance of standardizing the proportion/quantity of plants used in the preparation of Ayahuasca to avoid exacerbated variations in the alkaloid concentrations.

Regarding the ratios of Ayahuasca alkaloids prepared with fresh plants in the winter (samples A3 and A4), DMT/HRL, DMT/HRM, and DMT/THH were higher in plants from TF ecosystem, being 1.39; 0.35, and 0.21 respectively. Likewise, in the summer period (samples A2 and A13 in 1), the highest ratios were found for the samples prepared with plants from the TF ecosystem, being 2.66 for DMT/HRL, 0.46 for DMT/HRM, and 0.28 for DMT/THH, when compared with the samples prepared with plants from the CAMP ecosystem, showed THH/HRM ratio of 1.64 with TF plants and 0.88 with CAMP plants.

The ratio of THH/HRM both in the summer and winter seasons (samples A2 and A13, A3 and A4, in Supplementary Table 1) was higher and constant for samples of tea prepared with plants from TF ecosystem (1, 64), which is twice the ratio found by (Callaway, 2005), with samples from UDV. However, to our knowledge, the best ratio of these two alkaloids is still unknown, considering their entheogenic effects for religious, health purposes, and the treatment for chemical dependency.

Table 1. Concentration of alkaloids (mg/L) and cytotoxic effect (GI₅₀ g/ml) observed for Ayahuasca prepared with fresh *plants* and after drying.

Collect			Drying		Alkaloids (mg/L)					
Month/Year	Site	Season	Sample	No	Yes	DMT	HRL	HRM	THH	GI ₅₀
Aug/16	TF	S	A2	x		73,74	27,72	161,34	263,94	80,5 ± 5,1
			A14		60/60	37,3	15,7	181,9	79,4	nt
	Camp	W	A3	x		40,74	31,8	250,8	242,94	>150
			A12		60/60	31,62	14,52	110,76	100,62	>150
Jan/16	TF	W	A4	x		88,86	63,72	256,5	419,58	141,6 ± 13,9
			A10		50/50	39,72	30,66	198,0	230,88	150
	Camp	S	A13	x		41,04	52,14	310,56	274,2	nt
			A6		50/50	40,44	23,34	129,48	134,52	150
			A7	x		55,98	42,96	189,66	232,68	34,5 ± 7,3
			A8		40/40	65,1	51,54	240,12	256,32	nt
Nov/17	TF	S	A18		50/50	33,36	4,5	116,28	29,76	nt
			A11		40/45	52,0	33,4	238,8	206,6	nt
			A16		Sun	37,08	5,46	140,58	40,5	119,5 ± 0,5
	Camp	S	A5	x		81,42	41,88	246,3	290,58	>150
			A9		40/40	62,94	11,28	173,76	97,08	>150
			A17		50/50	55,5	19,2	149,28	96,54	>150
Feb/19	TF	W			43/45	108,36	39,78	165,3	127,8	111,9 ± 0,3
			Camp	S		43/45	98,94	29,76	119,1	111,42

TF = Terra Firme; Camp = Campinarana; Season: S = Summer, W = Winter; Samples: Ayahuasca prepared with fresh plants (A2-TF; A3-CAMP; A4-TF, A13-CAMP; A7-TF and A-5 CAMP); Drying : 60/60, 50/50, 40/40, 40/45, 43/45 = temperature (°C) of drying *P. viridis* leaves and *B. caapi* stems, respectively; Sun = leaves and stems dried in the sun; GI₅₀ (g/ml) = concentration of lyophilized tea necessary to inhibit the proliferation of HaCaT lineage cells by 50%; * approximate value depending on experimental values; nt= not tested

Table 2. Climatic variations occurred between summer 2016 and 2017 ecosystems CAM P and TF

Ecosystem	Date	T (°C)	Rainfall (mm)	Air humidity (%)	Water in the soil (%)
TF	Ago/16	28,07	4,72	72,92	62,94
TF	Nov/17	28,50	3,92	73,27	82,84
CAMP	Jan/16	28,41	0,99	63,08	52,40
CAMP	Nov/17	30,56	0,17	57,10	6,57

TF: Terra firme; CAMP: Campinarana; T: temperature. Given values are monthly averages.

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Table 3. Comparison of alkaloid concentration in Ayahuasca samples prepared with and without standardization from different sources. Quantified by HPLC.

Author	Standard	Source (n)	Samples (n)	DMT (mg/L)	HRL (mg/L)	HRM (mg/L)	THH (mg/L)
Callaway (2005)	No	4	20	160-5840	100-900	450-6250	450-5260
Lanaro et. al (2018)	No	1	9	402-2070	28-181	295-2894	850-2053
This study	Yes	1	20	41-108	28-64	161-311	239-420

This is the first study describing parameters to standardize procedures and proportions of plants (*P. viridis/B. caapi*) to be used in the preparation of Ayahuasca, which is key for comparison of samples from different regions, and thus to assess the environmental effects on alkaloid concentration. Quantification of alkaloids in Ayahuasca samples used in religious rituals, will allow a more accurate assessment of the real psychotropic effect of this beverage. Furthermore, considering that active plant compounds also have relationship with the species' genetic variability (Figueira et al., 2010; Gupta et al., 2017), further studies are necessary to understand the role of genetic variability in alkaloid variations in plant tissues.

To the present date, the preparations of Ayahuasca have been mainly done using fresh plant material. With the increasing popularity of the entheogenic effect and pharmacological benefits that Ayahuasca provides, applying post-harvesting treatments, as dehydration, may contribute to increase the quality of Ayahuasca used in countries where *P. viridis* and *B. caapi* cultivation is limited (Santos et al., 2017; Palhano-Fontes et al., 2018; Silveira et al., 2020).

In this context, this work analyzed the effect of the post-harvest drying process on the content of alkaloids in Ayahuasca tea prepared with *B. caapi* and *P. viridis*, dehydrated under the same temperatures (40, 50, 60°C, and at sun). Ayahuasca tea made with plants dried at 60 °C (A14 samples and A12, Table 1)

compared to the correspondent beverage prepared with fresh plants from both TF and CAMP ecosystems, demonstrated a decrease of 49, 43, 12, and 69.9% of DMT, HRL, HRM, THH content respectively. Whereas Ayahuasca samples with plants from CAMP showed a decrease of 22.4, 54.7, 56.0, and 59.3% for DMT, HRL, HRM and THH content, respectively. When samples from both TF and CAMP prepared with dehydrated plants at 50° C (samples A10 and A6, Table 1) are compared with their corresponding samples prepared with fresh plants (samples A4 and A13, Table 1) and with TF plant sample demonstrated 55.4, 51.8, 22.8 and 45.3 (mg/L) for DMT, HRL, HRM, and THH concentrations, respectively. Regarding samples with CAMP plants, the reduction of alkaloid concentration was 1.5, 55.2, 58.3, and 50.9 (mg/L) for DMT, HRL, HRM, and THH, sequentially. These results may have relationship with thermal instability of labile compounds in Ayahuasca tea, which can cause reactions during the drying process (Cernîşev, 2010; Orphanides et al., 2016).

On the other hand, comparing Ayahuasca samples made with plants dried at 40° C (samples A8 and A9, Table1) with their corresponding samples (samples A7 and A5, Table 1), an increase in alkaloid concentrations in Ayahuasca samples with TF plants, being 16.29, 19.97, 26.62, and 10.16% for DMT, HRL, HRM, and THH were detected. Whereas in samples with CAMP plants a reduction of 22.70, 73.07, 29.45, and 66.59 % for DMT, HRL, HRM, and THH was observed.

Drying temperatures at 50 and 60°C resulted in a high depletion of active compounds in Ayahuasca. Also, a high variation of compound depletion patterns, especially for DMT, HRL, and HHT was observed. This observation emphasizes the sensitivity of these compounds to these temperatures, and therefore are unsuitable for drying Ayahuasca plants, since thermal sensitivity and susceptibility to degradation affect the stability of the compound (Chua et al., 2019). Independently of the environment source, all the leaf samples of *P. viridis* darkened and stems of *B. caapi* became brittle after drying at 50 to 60°C (Orphanides et al., 2016). High temperature leads to irreversible and adverse chemical reactions that cause degradation of product quality (Cerniřev, 2010). While drying at 40°C showed unexpected results with reduction and increase of alkaloids content when compared with their corresponding samples, which may have been influenced by the morphological characteristics of the plants, that according to Chua et al. (2019) having also influenced the final quality by drying. Samples dried by direct solar heat also showed instability for DMT and β -carbolinic compounds concentration. Furthermore, drying in the sun. Furthermore, drying in the sun increases the risk of contamination by exposure of the material by unknown factors, therefore beverages prepared with these inputs could lead to adverse effects (Alibas et al., 2020).

In light of the distinct characteristics of each species that take part in Ayahuasca tea, the plant parts used in the tea preparation, and considering the concentrations found in Ayahuasca prepared with plants dried at 40 and 50°C, samples of Ayahuasca prepared with dried plants under different temperatures for each species were assessed, establishing conditions of (a) 45° C for stems and 40° C for leaves and (b) 45° C for stems and t 43° C for leaves (Fig. 5).

Considering the samples with stems and leaves dehydrated at 40/45 and 43/45°C respectively (Samples A11, A19 and A20, Table 1) the alkaloid concentration of HRL was low but relatively constant. THH/HRM ratios of both samples with CAMP and TF plants in winter and summer were close to 1:1, being constant in all samples. For DMT concentration of leaf samples dried at 40 to 43°C (sample A11, A19, A120, Table 1), leaves dried at 40°C had a low variation in the DMT content. However, there was also a low DMT content (52.0 mg/L) when compared to samples A19 and A20, prepared with leaves dehydrated at 43°C, that exhibited the greatest DMT concentration (108 and 98,94 mg/L) in TF and CAMP ecosystems, respectively. This result indicates that DMT could be sensitive to temperatures above 43°C, as is the case of trigonelline alkaloid during the coffee roasting process (Marcucci et al., 2013).

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Ratios of HHT/HRM 1:1 and 1:5 were found in report by Callaway (2005a) and Callaway et al. (2005b), respectively. These studies indicated that there could be a route to reduce HRM to HRL and from this to THH, however they did not investigate the interference of plant drying or the stability of the ratio between alkaloids.

Drying plants could be an answer to meet the growing demand for Ayahuasca products. Considering the synergistic action of the tea molecules, both the quantitative maintenance of DMT and the ratio between the β -carbolinic compounds appear to be fundamental for the psychotropic effects of Ayahuasca. The highest DMT concentration and greater stability between HHT/HRM ration found in Ayahuasca made with plants dried at 43 and 45°C, for *P. viridis* leaves and *B.caapi* stems, respectively, indicate that these temperatures are adequate for drying allowing the use in traditional Ayahuasca preparation.

Finally, the influence of variation in the chemical composition of Ayahuasca tea tested in vitro for antiproliferative activity was evaluated (Table 1, Figure 3). In vitro evaluation benefits from culturing cells in a conducive and controlled environment, besides ease and speed of assay execution and relatively low cost (Mori and Hara, 2013).

Furthermore, GI50 values greater than 30 g/ml are representative of samples that do not significantly affect cell proliferation (Fouche et al., 2008). Analyzing the results shown in Table 1 based on these criteria, 90% of all the samples analyzed exhibited GI50 above 150 g/ml, which means no cytotoxicity on the proliferation of normal human cells (HaCaT) (Fig. 6). Only sample A7, prepared with fresh plants collected from TF during the summer, and A20, prepared with dried leaves at 43°C and stems at 45°C collected in CAMP during the summer showed moderately cytotoxic activity when tested on immortal human keratinocytes (GI50 ≈ 30 g/ml, HaCaT) (Fig. 3).

Figure 2. Influence of drying temperature on the concentration (mg/L) of DMT, HRL, HRM and THH in Ayahuasca samples prepared with dehydrated *B. caapi* stems and *P. viridis* leaves.

However, the test is a target-oriented assessment. In the model defined by this study (immortal human keratinocytes, HaCaT), in vitro evaluation will help to highlight possible effects of Ayahuasca tea on the proliferation of normal tissues such as skin, mucous membranes and bone marrow (Muller and Milton, 2012). Thus, this evaluation of toxicity, considering the antiproliferative activity as a parameter, could potentially assist in refining screening samples for testing in vivo and enables a more targeted screening of samples to be evaluated (Lilienblum et al., 2008).

The evaluation of antiproliferative activity after 48h of exposure (Figure 3) followed the protocol developed by the National Institute of Cancer – USA (Monks et al., 1991). In this model, cytostatic activity can be expressed as the sample concentration necessary to inhibit cell proliferation by 50% (GI50) (Shoemaker, 2006).

Figure 3. Proliferation of immortal human keratinocytes (HaCaT) after 48 h of exposure to different samples of Ayahuasca tea (see Table 1 for collection and drying conditions for each sample).

Comparing these results of antiproliferative activity with the levels of DMT, HRL, HRM, and THH, as well as with the relative proportions between them (Table 1), there is no evident correlation between the variations observed for these compounds and the cytostatic effect observed in $GI_{50} \approx 30$ g/ml for samples A7 and A20. Therefore, a more in-depth assessment of the chemical profile of these samples compared to those that did not have a cytotoxic effect are necessary to identify the possible components involved in this antiproliferative effect. A systematic review of studies with humans has shown that acute, subacute and long-term use of Ayahuasca have low toxicity (R. G. Dos Santos et al., 2016). Moreover, assessments of biochemical parameters related to liver damage in serum in 22 volunteers who consumed Ayahuasca twice a month or more for at least one year indicate that chronic consumption of Ayahuasca in a religious context apparently does not affect liver function (Mello et al., 2019).

Furthermore, both DMT and HRM demonstrated a cytoprotective effect *in vitro* on different cell lines of human neurons submitted to hypoxia (Szabo et al., 2016) or by exposure to 6-hydroxydopamine (Katchborian-Neto et al., 2020). Moreover, harmine demonstrated antiproliferative activity in concentrations of approximately 50 μ M in breast tumor lines (Ding et al., 2019), while harmine derivatives have promising antiproliferative activity (<10 μ M) in different human tumor strains (Jadala et al., 2019; Sayed et al., 2020).

4. Conclusions

Variation of alkaloids concentration in Ayahuasca tea has relationship with the place and time of harvest of the species. Rainfall and water capacity of the soil showed to have straight relationship with the alkaloid contents of DMT, HRL, HRM, and THH in Ayahuasca. In the winter period, with higher rainfall, the alkaloids concentration in Ayahuasca prepared with plants from the TF ecosystem increases. Nevertheless, plants from CAMP seemed more adapted to water stress and the tea made with plants from this ecosystem had lower seasonal variation on the alkaloid's concentration.

Data reported herein demonstrated that drying temperature influences the quality of the components detected in the plants used to prepare Ayahuasca. Therefore, the drying parameters of *B. caapi* and *P. viridis* species should be standardized based on the morphological characteristics of each species. In this study, the most suitable conditions were achieved in a forced air circulation oven with temperatures of 43°C for leaves and 45°C for stems.

This allowed a constant and greater DMT concentrations, as well as maintained constant the quantitative proportion among the β -carbolines in Ayahuasca prepared with plants from either *Campinarana* or *Terra-Firme* ecosystems.

Regarding the *in vitro* cytotoxicity, the results indicated that variations of alkaloids concentrations in Ayahuasca prepared with dehydrated or fresh plants did not show cytotoxic effects on human keratinocytes with relationship to DMT, HRL, HRM, and THH. except for samples A7 and A20. Therefore, a more in-depth assessment of the chemical profile this samples compared to those that did not show a cytotoxic effect may identify the possible components involved in this slightly antiproliferative effect. ■

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5. REFERENCES

- Ab'Saber, A. N. (2002). Bases para o estudo dos ecossistemas da Amazônia brasileira. *Estudos Avançados*, 16(45), 7–30. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0103-40142002000200002>
- AgriTempo. (2018). *Pesquisa de dados meteorológicos para Presidente Figueiredo, AM*.
- Alvares, C. A., Stape, J. L., Sentelhas, P. C., de Moraes Gonçalves, J. L., & Sparovek, G. (2013). Köppen's climate classification map for Brazil. *Meteorologische Zeitschrift*, 22(6), 711–728. <https://doi.org/10.1127/0941-2948/2013/0507>
- Barbosa, R. I., & Miranda, I. de S. (2004). Fitofisionomia e diversidade vegetal das savanas de Roraima. In C. e S. J. M. Barbosa R. I., Xaud H. A. M. (Ed.), *Savanas de Roraima - Etnoecologia, Biodiversidade e Potencialidades Agrosilvipastoris* (pp. 61–78). FEMACT.
- Breeksema, J. J., Niemeijer, A. R., Erwin Krediet, ., Vermetten, E., Schoevers, R. A., & NI, J. B. (2020). Psychedelic Treatments for Psychiatric Disorders: A Systematic Review and Thematic Synthesis of Patient Experiences in Qualitative Studies. *CNS Drugs*, 34(925–926). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40263-020-00748-y>
- Callaway, J. C. (2005). Various alkaloid profiles in decoctions of banisteriopsis caapi. *Journal of Psychoactive Drugs*, 37(2), 151–155. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02791072.2005.10399796>
- Callaway, J. C., McKenna, D. J., Grob, C. S., Brito, G. S., Raymon, L. P., Poland, R. E., Andrade, E. N. O., Andrade, E. N. O., & Mash, D. C. (1999). Pharmacokinetics of Hoasca alkaloids in healthy humans. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 65(3), 243–256. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-8741\(98\)00168-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-8741(98)00168-8)
- Cavalcante, A. D., Cardoso, G. A., Oliveira, F. L. P. De, Bearzoti, E., Okuma, A. A., Duarte, L. P., & Vieira-filho, S. A. (2018). Influence of Environmental Factors and Cultural Methods on the Content of N,N-Dimethyltryptamine in Psychotria viridis (Rubiaceae). *Journal of the Brazilian Chemical Society*, 00(00), 1–11.
- Chua, L. Y. W., Chong, C. H., Chua, B. L., & Figiel, A. (2019). Influence of Drying Methods on the Antibacterial, Antioxidant and Essential Oil Volatile Composition of Herbs: a Review. *Food and Bioprocess Technology* (2019), 12, 450–476. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11947-018-2227-x>
- Ding, Y., He, J., Huang, J., Yu, T., Shi, X., Zhang, T., Yan, G., Chen, S., & Peng, C. (2019). Harmine induces anticancer activity in breast cancer cells via targeting TAZ. *International Journal of Oncology*, 54(6), 1995–2004. <https://doi.org/10.3892/ijo.2019.4777>
- Dos Santos, R. G., Balthazar, F. M., Bouso, J. C., & Hallak, J. E. (2016). The current state of research on ayahuasca: A systematic review of human studies assessing psychiatric symptoms, neuropsychological functioning, and neuroimaging. *Journal of Psychopharmacology*, 30(12), 1230–1247. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0269881116652578>
- Estrella-Parra, E. A., Almanza-Pérez, J. C., Francisco, ., & Alarcón-Aguilar, J. (2019). Ayahuasca: Uses, Phytochemical and Biological Activities. *Natural Products and Bioprospecting*, 9, 251–265. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13659-019-0210-5>
- Figueira, G. M., Ramelo, P. R., Ogasawara, D. C., Montanari, I., Zucchi, M. I., Cavallari, M. M., & Foglio, M. A. (2010). A set of microsatellite markers for Arrabidaea chica (Bignoniaceae), a medicinal liana from the Neotropics. *American Journal of Botany*, 97(7), 63–64. <https://doi.org/10.3732/ajb.1000145>
- Gaujac, A., Navickiene, S., Collins, M. I., Brandt, S. D., & Andrade, J. B. (2012). Analytical techniques for the determination of tryptamines and β -carbolines in plant matrices and in psychoactive beverages consumed during religious ceremonies and neo-shamanic urban practices. *Drug Testing and Analysis*, 4(7–8), 636–648. <https://doi.org/10.1002/dta.1343>
- Giumanini, G. A., Chiavari, G., Musiani, M. M., & Rossi, P. (1980). N-Permethylation of primary and secondary aromatic-amines. *Synthesis-Stuttgart*, 9, 743–746.
- Hamill, J., Hallak, J., Dursun, S. M., & Baker, G. (2019). Ayahuasca: Psychological and Physiologic Effects, Pharmacology and Potential Uses in Addiction and Mental Illness. *Current Neuropsychopharmacology*, 17(2), 108–128. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1570159X16666180125095902>

- Jadala, C., Sathish, M., Reddy, T. S., Reddy, V. G., Tokala, R., Bhargava, S. K., Shankaraiah, N., Nagesh, N., & Kamal, A. (2019). Synthesis and in vitro cytotoxicity evaluation of β -carboline-combretastatin carboxamides as apoptosis inducing agents: DNA intercalation and topoisomerase-II inhibition. *Bioorganic and Medicinal Chemistry*, 27(15), 3285–3298. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bmc.2019.06.007>
- Kaasik, H., Souza, R. C. Z., Zandonadi, F. S., Tófoli, L. F., & Sussulini, A. (2021). Chemical Composition of Traditional and Analog Ayahuasca. *Journal of Psychoactive Drugs*, 53(1), 65–75. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02791072.2020.1815911>
- Katchborian-Neto, A., Santos, W. T., Nicácio, K. J., Corrêa, J. O. A., Murgu, M., Martins, T. M. M., Gomes, D. A., Goes, A. M., Soares, M. G., Dias, D. F., Chagas-Paula, D. A., & Paula, A. C. C. (2020). Neuroprotective potential of Ayahuasca and untargeted metabolomics analyses: applicability to Parkinson's disease. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 255. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2020.112743>
- Labate, B. C., & Feeney, K. (2012). Ayahuasca and the process of regulation in Brazil and internationally - Implications and challenges.pdf. *International Journal of Drug Policy*, 23, 154–161. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drugpo.2011.06.006>
- Lanaro, R., Calemi, D. B. de A., Togni, L. R., Costa, J. L., Yonamine, M., Cazenave, S. de O. S., & Linardi, A. (2015). Ritualistic Use of Ayahuasca versus Street Use of Similar Substances Seized by the Police: A Key Factor Involved in the Potential for Intoxications and Overdose? *Journal of Psychoactive Drugs*, 47(2), 132–139. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02791072.2015.1013202>
- Liebelt, D. J., Jordan, J. T., & Doherty, C. J. (2019). Only a matter of time: the impact of daily and seasonal rhythms on phytochemicals. *Phytochemistry Reviews*, 18, 1409–1433. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11101-019-09617-z>
- Liesenfeld, V., Gentz, P., De Freitas, E. M., & Martins, S. (2019). Leaf morphology and anatomy of Asteraceae of the Pampas biome (sand-fields). *Flora: Morphology, Distribution, Functional Ecology of Plants*, 258. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.flora.2019.151418>
- Liu, W., Yin, D., Li, N., Hou, X., Wang, D., Li, D., & Liu, J. (2016). Influence of Environmental Factors on the Active Substance Production and Antioxidant Activity in *Potentilla fruticosa* L. and Its Quality Assessment. *Scientific Reports*, 6(July), 28591. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep28591>
- McKenna, D. J. (2004a). Clinical investigations of the therapeutic potential of ayahuasca: Rationale and regulatory challenges. *Pharmacology and Therapeutics*, 102(2), 111–129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pharmthera.2004.03.002>
- McKenna, D. J. (2004b). Clinical investigations of the therapeutic potential of ayahuasca: Rationale and regulatory challenges. *Pharmacology and Therapeutics*, 102(2), 111–129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pharmthera.2004.03.002>
- Mello, S. M., Soubhia, P. C., Silveira, G., Corrêa-Neto, N. F., Lanaro, R., Costa, J. L., & Linardi, A. (2019). Effect of Ritualistic Consumption of Ayahuasca on Hepatic Function in Chronic Users. *Journal of Psychoactive Drugs*, 51(1), 3–11. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02791072.2018.1557355>
- Miller, M. J., Albarracin-Jordan, J., Moore, C., & Capriles, J. M. (2019). Chemical evidence for the use of multiple psychotropic plants in a 1,000-year-old ritual bundle from South America. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 116(23), 11207–11212. <https://doi.org/10.1073/PNAS.1902174116>
- Miranda, O. F., Souza, S. E. X. F., Milan, R. J., Bueno, A. B., & Almeida, M. (2020). Influence of environment on the leaf morpho-anatomy and histochemical of the ayahuasca leaf: Populations cultivated in extra-Amazonian regions. *Acta Scientiarum Biological Sciences*, 42, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.4025/actascibiolsci.v42i1.50369>
- Moreira, L. J. da S. (2016). *Química, física, mineralogia e teores de metais pesados em solos do Estado do Amazonas*. Universidade Federal de Viçosa.
- Ncube, B., Finnie, J. F., & Van Staden, J. (2012). Quality from the field: The impact of environmental factors as quality determinants in medicinal plants. *South African Journal of Botany*, 82, 11–20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sajb.2012.05.009>
- Ng, Z. X., Yong, P. H., & Lim, S. Y. (2020). Customized drying treatments increased the extraction of phytochemicals and antioxidant activity from economically viable medicinal plants. *Industrial Crops and Products*, 155. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2020.112815>

- Orphanides, A., Goulas, V., & Gekas, V. (2016). Drying Technologies: Vehicle to High-Quality Herbs. *Food Engineering Reviews*, 8(2), 164–180. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12393-015-9128-9>
- Orsolini, L., Chiappini, S., Papanti, D., Latini, R., Volpe, U., Fornaro, M., Tomasetti, C., Vellante, F., & De Berardis, D. (2020). How does ayahuasca work from a psychiatric perspective? Pros and cons of the entheogenic therapy. *Human Psychopharmacology*, 35(3). <https://doi.org/10.1002/hup.2728>
- Osborn, A. E., Qi, X., Townsend, B., & Qin, B. (2003). Dissecting plant secondary metabolism - constitutive chemical defences in cereals. *New Phytologist*, 159(1), 101–108. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1469-8137.2003.00759.x>
- Pires, A. P. S., Dizoli, C., Oliveira, R. De, Moura, S., Dörr, F. A., Silva, W. A. E., & Yonamine, M. (2009). Gas Chromatographic Analysis of Dimethyltryptamine and b -Carboline Alkaloids in Ayahuasca , an Amazonian Psychoactive Plant Beverage. *Phytochemical Analysis*, 20, 149–153. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pca.1110>
- Rodrigues, T. E., Oliveira Junior, R. C., Santos, P. L., & Silva, P. R. O. (2001). Caracterização e classificação dos solos do município de Presidente Figueiredo, Estado do Amazonas. *Ministério Da Agricultura Pecuária e Abastecimento*, 50.
- Romeo, B., Karila, L., Martelli, C., & Benyamina, A. (2020). Efficacy of psychedelic treatments on depressive symptoms: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Psychopharmacology*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0269881120919957>
- Santos, B. W. L., de Oliveira, R. C., Sonsin-Oliveira, J., Fagg, C. W., Barbosa, J. B. F., & Caldas, E. D. (2020). Biodiversity of β -carboline profile of banisteriopsis caapi and ayahuasca, a plant and a brew with neuropharmacological potential. *Plants*, 9(7), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants9070870>
- Santos, R. G. dos, & Hallak, J. E. C. (2020). Ayahuasca, an ancient substance with traditional and contemporary use in neuropsychiatry and neuroscience. *Epilepsy & Behavior Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yebeh.2019.04.053>
- Sayed, A. R., Gomha, S. M., Taher, E. A., Muhammad, Z. A., El-Seedi, H. R., Gaber, H. M., & Ahmed, M. M. (2020). *One-Pot Synthesis of Novel Thiazoles as Potential Anti-Cancer Agents*. <https://doi.org/10.2147/DDDT.S221263>
- Silveira, G. de O., Santos, R. R. G. dos, Lourenço, F. R., Rossi, G. N., Hallak, J. E. C., & Yonamine, M. (2020). Stability evaluation of DMT and Harmala alkaloids in ayahuasca tea samples. *Molecules*, 25(9), 5–7. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules25092072>
- Silveira, L. H. C., Rezende, A. V., & Vale, A. T. do. (2013). Teor de umidade e densidade básica da madeira de nove espécies comerciais amazônicas. *Acta Amazonica*, 43(2), 179–184.
- Souza, R. C. Z., Zandonadi, F. S., Freitas, D. P., Tófoli, L. F. F., & Sussulini, A. (2019). Validation of an analytical method for the determination of the main ayahuasca active compounds and application to real ayahuasca samples from Brazil. *Journal of Chromatography B: Analytical Technologies in the Biomedical and Life Sciences*, 1124, 197–203. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jchromb.2019.06.014>
- Szabo, A., Kovacs, A., Riba, J., Djurovic, S., Rajnavolgyi, E., & Frecska, E. (2016). The Endogenous Hallucinogen and Trace Amine N,N-Dimethyltryptamine (DMT) Displays Potent Protective Effects against Hypoxia via Sigma-1 Receptor Activation in Human Primary iPSC-Derived Cortical Neurons and Microglia-Like Immune Cells. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, 10, 423. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2016.00423>
- Tupper, K. W. (2008). The globalization of ayahuasca: Harm reduction or benefit maximization? *International Journal of Drug Policy*, 19(4), 297–303. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drugpo.2006.11.001>
- Zarur, J. (1943). Um comentário sobre a classificação de Koppen. *Revista Brasileira de Geografia*, 2, 250–254.

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